

**From Paper to Platform: Exploring Sustainable
Pedagogies through Mobile-Assisted Language
Learning.**

**By
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Declaration of Originality

I, Sundus Anwar affirm that my Dissertation titled: From Paper to Platform: Exploring Sustainable Pedagogies through Mobile-Assisted Language Learning is a genuine work and that it contains 15359 words, exclusive of preliminary section, maps, diagrams, tables, statistical appendices and references.

I also confirm that I have fully acknowledged to all those individuals and organizations who have contributed to the research for this Dissertation.

It is explicitly understood that Greenwich University reserves the right to check originality of manuscript both manually & electronically.

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Abstract

This study explores the impact of mobile-assisted language learning (MALL) on reading comprehension among 5th-grade learners in a virtual learning environment. Using a mixed-method approach, 50 participants were engaged with the mobile application "GetEpic" to examine and analyze the autobiographical work, "The Diary of Anne Frank". Results show that MALL significantly enhances student enthusiasm, the ability to make complex inferences and vocabulary attention as compared to traditional book-based methods. Beyond pedagogical efficiency this research also explores mobile technology in promoting digital ecology, and it facilitates the paperless classrooms which reduce the environmental footprint or resource production. The study also concludes that the interrogation of mobile reading applications can be a sustainable solution for modern language education because it offers effective and ecologically responsible outcomes.

Keywords: MALL, Reading Comprehension, Digital Ecology, Sustainability, Virtual Learning.

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Chapter 1: Introduction

Background of the Study:

Reading is a skill that is developed. Reading and learning are the processes which are interlinked. From the beginning of time the human race has introduced new ways to write their views and read them afterwards. From carving of stones, wood to paper and now on the internet in the form of E-Books. With the advent of the Internet and digital tools such as computers, laptops, iPods and mobile phones, new ways of reading and learning have been introduced. Teaching in the 21st century, teachers need to embrace new technologies and new tools which cater for learners' needs and help them learn English. These learners are called digital natives worldwide. Now, The Pandemic has induced technology a lot, it has given more and more opportunities to teachers and made work easier because of various Educational Applications. From taking classes on digital platforms to giving reading assignments through Mobile Applications have become a new normal. Get Epic is American subscription based mobile reading application that has been introduced to get kids able to read easily on one platform. CEO and Co-founder Suren Markosian introduced this mobile reading application as this company has almost 200 million users. This mobile reading application supports stories for kids only. Millions of users around the world are benefiting from it. In 2016 it was ranked as one of the best applications for mobile reading. It can easily be downloaded in mobiles and I pads, they can carry it around with them.

Scope of the Study:

The use of mobile applications can assist with elocution instructing and learning as it takes into consideration individualized guidance which can happen outside the classroom, mitigating the typical nervousness students experience in real language classrooms.

Statement of the Problem:

The increase of technology went to another level after the pandemic; students shifting to virtual learning do show a lot of interest in online mobile applications because of their easy accessibility, better material, in apt words smartphones is lighter and more affordable than computers. Using smartphones offers numerous environmental benefits, including ubiquitous access to offline materials, cloud-based storage like Google Drive and very enhanced connectivity. Devices facilitate the idea of learning on the go, which fosters creative progress in language acquisition. Numerous studies have validated and experimented on these benefits, such as in the Japanese context and Heil et al. (2016), who have explored challenges and nutrients in mobile applications. However, as noted by Blau and Shamir-Inbal (2017), many teachers have still been struggling to identify good authentic sources for the children for reading comprehension. This research aims to bridge that gap and identify effective mobile channels that support both future educators and current learners in a sustainable and digital ecology.

Objectives of the Study:

The primary objectives of this research are as follows:

To investigate the impact of mobile applications on students' reading comprehension:

This involves analyzing how digital platforms influence the cognitive processing of texts in a virtual environment.

To evaluate the effectiveness of Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL): The study aims to determine the pedagogical value of MALL as a sustainable and accessible alternative to traditional classroom materials.

To identify benefits for learners: Beyond immediate academic results, the study explores how mobile integration supports lifelong learning habits and digital literacy.

To assess cognitive literacy outcomes: The final goal is to observe the extent to which mobile applications facilitate specific reading strategies, including:

- Comprehension Monitoring: Learners ability to track their own understanding.
- Synthesizing Connections and Inferences: Learners being able to draw logical conclusions from digital content.
- Vocabulary Acquisition: Maximizes lexical range through interactive tools.
- Structural Analysis: Using and understanding digital organization and interface design to find meaning from complex texts.

Research Questions:

1. How effective are mobile applications in enhancing learners' reading comprehension?
2. How does it help students understand monitoring comprehension?
3. How do students make inferences and connections?
4. How does it enhance students' understanding of new vocabulary?

5. How will students use structure and organization in order to grasp the comprehension?
6. How are online reading applications different from book reading?

Research Assumptions:

Mobile Assisted Technology may help in student learning more because of easy access.

Students can make sense of the phrases and ideas.

Students can connect clues and infer the given information more effectively.

Students learn and understand new words easily through online read aloud word meanings.

Students can easily summaries and order events by reading online comprehension.

Students read with engagement because they are user friendly

It also helps students during pandemic crisis because of their easy access

Definition of the Key Terms:

Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL) shows a shift toward widespread and portable education. According to Shield and Kukulska-Hulme (2008), MALL moves forward simple content delivery toward supported cooperation and interaction. This study constructs on the foundational work of Thornton and Houser (2005), who demonstrated the effectiveness of mobile devices in linguistic education, proving that portable technology facilitates "learning on the go" more successfully than traditional stationary methods.

Reading Comprehension in a digital context, reading comprehension shows the intellect's capacity to grasp meaning from screen-based texts. Duke and Pearson (2021) highlight that the "science of reading" needs specific instructional strategies to be efficient. This research investigates how digital platforms like "Get Epic" provide the scaffolded support and learning necessary for learners to master reading comprehension in a virtual environment, as highlighted by Kim and Burkhauser (2020) regarding content literacy interventions.

Digital Ecology means the interaction between technology, the learner, and their environmental space. This study shows the mobile device as an ecological tool that eliminates the "material weight" of education. As explored by Blau and Shamir-Inbal (2017), the "voice of the teacher" in a paperless classroom is important for developing a digital ecology that is both pedagogically efficient and resource friendly.

Virtual Learning was accelerated by global shifts in the educational sector. Egbert (2020) states this transition in schools as a "pandemic of task engagement," where digital tools were made the primary medium for instruction. This study works with the insights of Radia (2019), who concludes that Moodle-based and blended learning environments can offer unique views into EFL learners' progress when physical classrooms are inaccessible.

Sustainability in education involves creating channels that are resilient and environmentally friendly and responsible. UNESCO (2016) advocates for "Education for People and Planet," emphasizing on the need for sustainable futures for everyone. Furthermore, Zhan (2020) highlights the online self-regulation with broader

sustainability, suggesting that digital learning models can help in long-term viability of educational systems by minimizing physical waste and growing learner autonomy.

Delimitations:

In Pakistan most people don't have mobile access, internet bandwidth issue, we are living in underdeveloped countries lack these resources. es are user friendly

The limitation can be in terms of Smartphone accessibility and if it supports the software and not all software, teachers not interested in technology training or inhibitions regarding technology, worked with one organization for a better result.

The access of students was only limited to the subjects that were studying in the school system and they have the means to help in conduction of the research

Chapter 2: Literature Review

The emergence of Internet, Smartphone's and ICT (Information and Computer Technology) have revolutionized the whole idea of teaching and learning inside and outside the classroom. Now a days there are very few individuals who are not seen with a Smartphone as the world progresses so is the Era of Smartphone progressing and developing. A Smartphone is a phone that has a lot of advanced functions. A typical Smartphone features a high-resolution touch screen display, Wi-Fi connectivity, Web browsing capabilities, and the capacity to accept advanced applications. These advanced applications have made life easier and proactive, everyone around is known of everything the level of awareness and the level of knowing is reaching its epitome.

“People have adapted this new and exciting technology as an important role in their everyday life (Darko-Adjei, 2019, p. 1). Globally the vast explosions of smartphones and devices and applications related to it have transformed learning and teaching where developing nations are no exception. We have seen a number of scholars who have done research on mobile phones and their use a) driving performance (Catherine Regina Heil, 2016) b) Satisfaction with life (Heil, 2016) .The research showed how smart phones have changed and remodeled life. We see the insights given by a lot of tech tycoons as well and how they virtual learning in changing our lives.

Within the next decade, it is likely that the computer may become an educational ally for all kids. Indeed, computers will almost certainly become an integral part of all classroom learning. However, the computer is still in its infancy, and its influence on education is only beginning. (JIANG, 2018) showed that approximately 77 percent of America's inhabitant Population owned a Smartphone (JIANG, 2018) looking at the report shared by (Kemp, 2020) shows that around 76.38 million internet users are in Pakistan and from those 37 million have access to Smartphone applications.

The research on Covid-19 outbreaks done by Journal of Medical Research in 2020 shows that Mobile apps have been used for training, information and rapidly offer effective and usable tools for managing. The proliferation and excessive updates have changed the style of learning. Citizens, teachers and professionals consider mobile apps to be a valuable tool for addressing critical challenges posed by the pandemic, such as reducing the burden on schools, providing access to credible information, tracking students' assessments and overall performance, and discovering new predictors.

If we see the study done by (Muhammad Mooneeb Alia, 2020) also showed how students enjoy the use of MALL in their learning both inside and outside the Classroom, students also felt that MALL helped them in getting information quickly and was more enjoyable. Mobile learning as stated by (Kukulka-Hulme, 2006) that there are three main things that mobile technology supports: improves access, potentials are explored that can change teaching and learning, a gateway is made with the international standard teachings and learning. The expansion of the educational software industry has offered a financial incentive for R&D activities. Large sums of money are being invested by computer manufacturers in the marketing and creation of language arts and reading software and applications. For example, the Khan Academy is a built-in school in itself, through proper streams and lines of explanation it has taken its special paradigm in the education field just like this if looking at language learning we see duo lingo as a pioneer for closing the deal.

Use of Mobile Phones for learning a new Language:

Mobile learning is going under rapid changes and making a big difference in the rapid evolution of Learning. Earlier generations had mobile learning but with a lot of complex designs (Kukulka-Hulme, 2007), the use of these devices was really hard and not so user friendly. In the article proposed by (Reinders, 2010) he also stated twenty ideas for using mobile phones in the Language Classroom. Some of them are organizing language samples by using free programs, the text Messaging features help in vocabulary learning, using the smart phone for a language exchange, using the smart phone for

engaging in more reading material, the teachers can access a number of websites for presentation and better interaction.

Motivation and Attitudes of Learners:

MALL helps learners learn without fear. The learners can be engaged in activities and learning by their personal needs and their learning pace. This makes the students more comfortable and they engage more in learning as CALL the new modern, impacted way of Language learning as (Egbert, 2020) in his book showed the use of CALL has become a basic necessity and use in the new modern classroom. CALL is a set of software tools aimed to help people learn languages. These tools are focused, motivating and highly effective with students. Levy (1997) describes CALL as a discipline that covers “the search for and examines of computer language learning and further on teaching it” (Egbert, 2020, p. 1).

Mobile technologies are rapidly attracting new users, providing increasing capacity, and allowing more sophisticated use. This influences cultural practices and enables new contexts for teach (Fatemipour, 2017).The integration of such technologies into teaching and learning has been more gradual, as educators need to understand how they can be effectively used to support various kinds of learning (Kukulka-Hulme, 2007) and develop effective methods and materials for mobile assisted language learning (MALL), a specialization of mobile learning (mlearning). The main characteristics of mobile learning, such as permanency, accessibility, immediacy, interactivity, situating of instructional activities, are summarized and introduced by (BAHLOUL, 2016). The 21st century made us all more tech savvy and developed our greater understanding on how we

can benefit from mobile devices. Mobile phones have revolutionized our way of thinking and working. We all are now connected with the world more clearly and we see how after the Covid.19 Pandemic we have started really seeing a major shift in the use of mobile applications,

In Pakistan we have 68% users on smart phones, the age group of 10-20 has around 11% where they use Smartphone so to incorporate a more effective tool at this age would help them take benefit and use technology in a better and easier way. 52 % access the internet on Edge, 3G and GPRS.

More than two third of the world population is now connected to mobile services meaning we have mobile users equal to that according to real time data from GSMA. According to GSMA Intelligence's new results, there are 5.20 billion unique cell phone users in the world today.

The extensive use and abundance of mobile devices has not been ignored by scholars and educators. Adding to this, there has been an increasing need for and interest in learning languages in many non-English-speaking countries, especially English. As a result, this increasing curiosity in language learning has driven researchers to look for new instruments which could facilitate productive language teaching.

A variety of studies have been performed to this end on mobile learning in general and mobile learning since the beginning of the 2000s smart phones, in fact, to account for the utility of language integration technology teachings. These experiments have shown that mobile learning is powerful and scalable in the area of learning. It feels like it can solve time and space limitations, encouraging learners to research whenever and wherever (Chung, 2007).

Portability is a feature which helps users of mobile phones to take their devices everywhere they go and use them. Social interactivity refers to the willingness of apps to share data to connect with each other. Sensitivity to context is a function that helps Smartphone users to capture data relating to the current location, climate, and time.

Digital Ecology and Paperless Classrooms:

The transition from computer assisted language learning and going towards Mobile Assistant language learning showed more than just a technological upgrade. The shift towards digital ecology. Centralizing learning materials with mobile devices institutions can actually bring forward paperless classrooms that is a significant important environmental footprint reduction.

Paper has a huge mass production and is a primary driver for deforestation and high carbon emission which is which is highly unsustainable and impacts the global ecological system. MALL addresses this by replacing physical textbooks, worksheets and language Labs with multifunctional digital tools. This materialization of the classroom promotes a greener future and helps in conserving natural resources and reducing waste. As noted by Blau and Shamir-Inbal (2017), the paperless classroom is not merely a choice but a reality of modern life that increases the transparency and efficiency of the learning process. More, integrating sustainability Focus content into mobile assisted language learning such as vocabulary related to sustainable Development Goals or transforming the mobile devices into tools for both linguistic proficiency and environmental stewardship. Emphasized in the {Citation} global education monitoring report, ICT is not a pedagogical convenience but it's a powerful tool for sustainability by improving the

efficiency of resource use (p. 24). If you adopt a Mobile Assistant language learning educators can actually align this with the international mandate that education must be transformative and educators can move forward and create carbon neutral places which give more significance to digital delivery over physical waste

Technology eliminates FEAR:

Reading and learning should be filled with fun so students feel learning is easier and less hectic. Tablets, laptops and especially phones have built up another revolution for students. We see a wide range of acceptance from them also easy access makes them more inclined on learning from phones. The scenario of judgment, called out and being graded after explanation also stops. In each pointer the classroom setting schools have makes students feel a societal pressure they develop a sense of neglect and sense of tire ship. The belief that virtual learning is the new normal and can stop a lot of inhibitions faced by students also includes fear. Fear is a very big factor why some of the students do not take learning seriously. Keeping the Pakistani classroom in mind we see a big chunk of it being centralized on how well and fluent a student is able to speak in English Language. English language Learning or any other Language learning requires a lot of courage and if in any case the students feelings are put at show he/she might go in anxiety as (Zhan, 2020) stated how anxiety is an uneasy and uncertain cognitive state and leads to stops in learning of Language . They also showed how when learning a language the anxiety is to be blamed over negative reactions emotionally in the course of learning a new language.

The emergence of CALL:

The way computer class room orientation has changed to integrated classrooms means that people who were using computer studies just as a subject are now integrating as an essential key element of the studies. The CALL (Computer Assisted Language Learning) was established in the early 1980s and is highlighted by so many writings (Liu, 2020). Learners using electronic dictionaries for pronunciation improvement and practice. Learners using websites extensions attached on chrome like grammar, ginger software and reverse etc. all these added extensions help learner read and write without inhibition, also when we see the effects of this software. they help learners in auto checking and self-evaluating their own writing. The emergence of CALL has helped teachers and educators to bridge the gap in learning. The use of computers has become so normal in learning and teaching

Teachers and students can use computers to help them generate and finish stories.

Interactive fiction programmers, like simulations, allow students to create their own stories using computer-generated tale fragments. Students will not be able to compose all of the stories due to the large number of alternative tale outcomes.

The problem with reading applications is that we see a variety of hazards, some of them being Copy protection schemes provide one answer to the problem, but software developers and publishers are looking beyond these costly schemes. Site licensing and software rentals are two potential solutions. Also, some newer software programs allow the buyer to make as many copies as desired, but copies can be made only from the purchased disk; so the authenticity remains and teachers are open to licensed and better material.

Based on computer-based instructional studies, it became evident that computers can teach reading, reduce instructional time, and be a fun method to learn. The CALL phenomena have been coined in the computer literature to describe this image.

Mobile Learning:

(Shield, 2008) Suggested that rather than looking at mobile devices as hindrances and stops in the writing should be used effectively by educators. Mobile devices offer learning experiences which can engage and educate learners more. It's amazing to see now that students completed a whole academic year with the help of mobile phones and through mobile learning, they were able to contribute to the larger picture of their learning. (Darko-Adjei, 2019) Noted that "Not only that, Distance education has always thrived on the backs of technological advancements". We also noted how students can now access complete lecture materials and access classes wherever and whenever. It also allows students to enroll for classes online, take an exam or a semester using a designated or get registered on different learning management systems, and have a digital group conversation through different interactive platforms.

Now working in a school English educators have realized they cannot take out mobile learning from the writing, reading, listening and speaking so they have to find ways to incorporate the two together. (Nasir, 2017) Stated in their findings that a mobile phone can be used for educational purposes. To add on to more the use of some major applications was also shown in their study. Their study catered to PDF reader, offline dictionaries and other apps. The same study also showed that how students spent their time some spent it on using social media .There were two main functions seen what students performed when they were accessing mobile phones. Given internet connection,

people priorities chatting and social media as their primary modes of communication on their mobile phones. According to certain research, when teens and youngsters use the internet, social media is the most often visited and accessed medium. So, through good content and better informative articles we can promote reading and not to forget this also shows how much English is necessary as a 40% content on the media is written in English.

The research from (Gustavo García Botero, 2018) also stated how students preferred their smart phones compared to computers .If designed properly, this mobility and use of connectivity of mobile phones can lead to a better learning of mobile assisted language learning (Deborah Yapp, 2021)

In the paper by (Kukulska-Hulme, 2007) shows how the use of mobile applications can be seen they have a big debate over what role does mobile technology play here? Is mobile computing pushing us closer to – or further away from – usable computing ideals? Mobile device user interfaces are frequently straightforward, yet each manufacturer has their own.

(Kukulska-Hulme, 2006) Has highlighted three key motives as enhancing access, investigating the possibilities for improvements in teaching and learning, and aligning with larger institutional or corporate goals. We see how Practitioners and researchers are interested in collaborative learning, students' appreciation of their own learning process, learning consolidation, and ways to help learners see a subject differently than they would have without the use of mobile devices, where the emphasis is on changing teaching and learning. Also, Just-in-time learning and learning management assistance are also hot topics. There is an understanding that new technology may play a role in

lowering cultural and communication barriers, as well as influencing attitudes and study habits.

Every week, a new "reading" or "language arts" program is announced by a developer. Although the variety of programmers available may be beneficial for reading teaching, instructors want assistance in learning about the software available and picking the software that is most suited for their learners.

By looking at the Criteria for using non print media in the reading curriculum developed by the IRA

Before using audiovisual technology in the classroom, teachers should be adequately educated in its use.

- To prevent wasting important classroom teaching time, non-print material should be ready to use prior to its planned usage. The room's amenities should be properly prepared ahead of time (i.e., electrical outlets, adaptors, seating, extension cords).
- To ensure understanding of the ideas and concepts offered, content should be debated and student knowledge tested and revised.
- Materials must promote and be compatible with the school district's overall instructional goals.
- Resources must be appropriate for the pupils' age, emotional, intellectual and social development, as well as their interests.
- It should give a backdrop of information that allows students to make informed decisions in their everyday lives.
- Notes and data should entice students to read, write, listen, and think creatively.

- Transcripts, books and articles that represent society's heterogeneous nature and culture.
- Respect for minorities, women, and ethnic groups must be emphasized in the materials.
- The materials must be of appropriate technical quality and proper spacing, with intelligible narration, synced images, illustrations and sound that is read aloud option, and other features.
- Materials should be chosen for their aesthetic value, allowing learners to develop a greater awareness for the world around them.
- Affective reactions should be encouraged, and humanistic issues should be pursued.
- Teachers should be aware of the applications the play store offers and check the following questions concerning computer-based reading and language arts packages.

Tell me which computer is used to execute the application and whether any extra equipment is required.

Is a color monitor required for the program or the software works with black and white?

Is it necessary to have two or four gb for the program?

Is a voice synthesizer required for the program?

Is there a requirement for more memory in the program?

Is there anything more the app requires?

Also see how the program will fit into the curriculum.

What is the proper grade level?

What kinds of learners could benefit from the program?

What kinds of teaching methods and teaching styles would be appropriate for the program?

What kinds of materials for reading and language are compatible?

What are the time requirements for the activities?

Tell me what the pupils are reading on and off the screen.

Do they read aloud?

Do they understand what you're saying?

Are the learners able to read words or sentences by themselves?

Do they have the ability to read questions?

Do they understand syllables?

Do they know how to read letters?

Will learners be able to follow the directions for the program or activity?

Is there anything else they can read or recognize?

Tell me about the substance of the show.

Does it have any instruction activities?

Are there any opportunities for practice?

Are there any vocabulary exercises?

Do you have any comprehension exercises?

Do you have any study skills activities?

Are there any grammar exercises?

Any activities involving syllables or the alphabet?

Any interactive and skill set games to play, which focus on particular strands like reading, writing, listening or speaking?

Is there any kind of testing going on?

Are there any other options?

Is there more than one activity on a single book provided or can you add them?

The description of the audio (and voice) presentations to the teachers should be given.

Is there any speaking in the program? When is it going to happen? What is the reason behind this? (spoken in a synthesized manner)

voice from the future of digital speech human voice)

Is there any non-speech sound in the program? When is it going to happen? What is the reason behind this?

Is it possible for me or the pupils to regulate or remove the problem?

What is the volume?

Be aware about the reading and language objectives and goals mentioned by the curriculum.

Do teachers have any aims or aims (achievement, motivation, behavior, management)?

Is there a set of objectives and targets for learners to achieve such as better reading, better fluency etc?

Are there any objectives and goals that match the educational criteria of my state or locality?

Are there any objectives or goals that align with or connect with test objectives and goals?

Reading Comprehension:

Bad readers avoid engaging with the written words, which leads to unfavorable attitudes about school and learning. The majority of school and teacher issues stem from students' inability to read. Lack of reading skills presents itself in behavior patterns that are misinterpreted by teachers as misbehaving, being ill-mannered, or even unintelligent, rather than as not being able to read. (Weikle and Hadadian 2003:181) stated that Many educationalists continue to dispute the benefits of technology in nurturing literacy skills, and as a result, learners and students who enter the educational system with a lack of reading skills and technological capabilities are more likely to fail to meet their educational goals

Reading develops an approach that makes students accept the differences between them. Sometimes inhibitions lead to leaving a certain course which at all costs should be avoided. The understanding of this can be stated by how one can influence and target their learners in the most approachable way

This comprehensive approach must unavoidably integrate with family and community contexts: forging strong, respectful partnerships to understand the students' needs and build on learners' experiences and ideas, as well as to reinforce the basic elements of healthy learning so children's health and well-being are not at risk. Importance of the solid, supportive connections that allow students to benefit from effective learning. The opportunities in the cognitive, social, and emotional domains. We emphasize that all of these elements of education are interactive and linked, and that they

must be structured to operate together in a closely integrated manner. So, as students learn with understanding and make more ways for other learners to see education as a basic fundamental towards prosperity not as a burden or stress filled institution

English teaching and learning summons four major skills of reading, writing, listening and speaking. The Private Schools in Pakistan place English as a compulsory subject and a basic admission requirement. But in practice if we look at the government education sectors of Pakistan, we do not see the implementation of this process throughout but through the revolution of mobile technology it is possible to make the gaps meet.

Reading is a very intricate, complex and complicated process, teaching reading has to be taken very seriously. A child learns the word “that” without using phonetics, only by his/her memorization.

There are a number of interventions that are found to be effective but the major components are the same characteristics of quality of teaching, regular exposure to an age level reading material. (Kashif Ishaq, 2020) Thinks that reading is a continuous, interactive, and dynamic activity in which students can build on past knowledge to gain new insights. Reading helps in vocabulary it shapes a student’s mind for more perspectives and emphasizes on different and new ideas. Reading also helps in pinning the past experiences of the students. Reading gauges the knowledge one has and implements new parallels in it. Reading comprehensions develop a student’s understanding and makes them more mentally sound.

“Neurologists have found that the process of reading is done on the brain's left side. At all ages, good and sound reader’s exhibit: strong activation in the brains back side with lesser in the front. A reader that is struggling shows under activation on both the sides”. (Bibby, 2018)

(grönlund, 2012) According to the findings, a greater emphasis on vocabulary in the classroom is required to make accurate forecasts about reading abilities. Comprehension is the basic essence of reading and it accounts for a supportive effective extraction of meaning by a written passage. The goal of engagement is to keep readers cognitively and behaviorally active, therefore a balance of interest, self-regulation, motivation, reading attitude, and text involvement should all be considered when assessing reader engagement (Rifat Kamasak, 2020).As the times have changed now the role of the teachers has very rapidly changed and for an English Instructor it becomes more and more challenging on how to bring the students (Hoi, 2020).

Reading requires a lot of attention and retention. Similarly, educators and authors should regard reading as a tactic to engage readers, obtain related information from texts, increase their academic vocabulary, and engage in critical reflection to boost comprehension. (James S. Kim, 2020) Implies that the comprehension accounts on the ability to capture the appropriate response to the data provided in the text. Similarly, reading interventions in the classroom allow students to engage in critical reflection and text comprehension, as well as use logic to generate adequate responses in comprehension. Reading interventions in the classroom, meanwhile, allow students to participate in critical reflection and text comprehension, as well as employ logic to develop appropriate comprehension responses (BAHLOUL, 2016)

When students are given pre-reading assignments that build their level of engagement and promote critical thinking and understanding of text, their level of comprehension improves by (Abakah, 2014)

As (Adhitas Dewi Helda Ningrum, 2021) say that when they get encouraged only then they get the comply to read more and when reading engagement becomes high is when they are encouraged and so this means when a student wants to read they should be given ample encouragement and resources to make their understanding more better.

Similarly (Nell K. Duke, 2021) enlightened the main contexts of strategies that promote productive and sound methods how teacher can make a big change in students writing and reading style , special reading comprehension , he stated that teachers should adopt and churn up explicit teaching methods and styles specially in reading comprehension during reading activities.

In this age we need more digital tools for better reading so students on the go ,on to a different place can always have access to reading.

Children who have a more populated area can hear a wider vocabulary so when the students who

Monitoring comprehension through learning is also a very important aspect of reading. It helps to distinguish whether the student has grasped the ideas through reading or not. The reading and rereading also proves to be a very strong part of students' understanding. The idea of connecting sense with what one reads only comes with a strong grasp of known knowledge. Sense is only made when the sentence structure and use of words is clear in one's mind and the ideas are making clear visuals in the mind of the reader.

Connections and Inferences:

The connections are the basic understanding of a reader Starting from a local cohesion of “matching pronouns and nouns” to matching the right syntax in the sentence. The use of the right words is very important and once you read and keep on reading you develop a sense of cohesion and coherence. The idea of reading comprehension is not only restricted to local cohesion but also shows the connections of different “global coherence inferences' ' which include the cause and effect, reasons for particular actions and which and what point of views are shown in the material. (Liu, 2020) Synthesizes past taxonomies to establish criteria for studying this topic. He discusses three cohesion processing study parameters: (a) kind (causal, temporal, and additive), (b) polarity in terms of positive and negative and (c) direction is not done being on (forward, bidirectional, and backward).

Vocabulary the way a person understands is defined by their vocabulary. The way one speaks is defined by one’s vocabulary. Young children usually exhibit a very limited vocabulary, but vocabulary grows very fast with time. New words are constantly being heard, learned, and understood by children. To learn, a child must be introduced to new vocabulary. The more you read the more key vocabulary words you will encounter.

Long lists of terms memorized in isolation or working through vocabulary self-improvement books may deceive you into thinking you're learning new words, but the meanings won't remain, and you won't be exposed to them in real writing.

In order to realize what context a word is used in and how the words affect and carries forward the reading. In order to build vocabulary, there should be a daily drilling of new words that students learn. The vocabulary can only persist if the words learnt are

practiced that same day or used in some sentence formation. A study shown by (Chung, 2007) shows how through their application on vocabulary learning they were able to show that the proposed system for individualized English vocabulary acquisition has been successfully deployed on a personal digital assistant (PDA). Because of the effective and flexible learning mode for English vocabulary learning, the experimental results suggested that the suggested system could clearly increase learners' learning performances and interests.

A large vocabulary not only aids reading ability, but it also improves a reader's fluency. A learner can't improve as a reader unless they expand their vocabulary. Young children learn vocabulary via a variety of sources, including school, television, radio, listening to or conversing with adults and peers, and reading. Also, we see that reading fluently necessitates a fluid flow of information across the brain. It is necessary for readers to read aloud and practice in order to improve their fluency. Students can improve their fluency by using strategies like partnered reading or small group reading. Reading aloud and listening to the reading aloud is another effective approach to improve fluency.

Reading is a very drawn-out task so if there are numerous new words on the page, and looking into parts of words in the word reference is tedious and debilitating. A feeble jargon is without a doubt a huge hindrance to great understanding perception

Understanding and Making sense of a text by understanding the 'gist', how the ordering events have taken place in reading and how well the identification has been done .The identification is only completed when we see a the picture in front and that is only possible if students can comprehend words and their understanding, The context of

ordering and listing down events is only seen we students have a better and clear knowledge about how and when

Summarizing main ideas and writing your own summary of the understanding, drawing on knowledge of text conventions, this includes all sorts of conventions from top to bottom, social, economic or individual. The reader has to show their own take on words which highlights the different forms, and features of a prominent structure of a writing.

(Hijril Ismail, 2020) Proved that the best and smart apt reading procedures mainly consist of a few basic reading strategies such as reorganization, literal comprehension and inferences. Moreover, these techniques help motivating the students and making them feel like they are able to read eliminates the fear of language from them. As quoted in the **TESOL** reading of “suggestopedia” suggested that to improve learning in English Language Learning the facilitator has to eliminate fear and make sure the learner feels welcomed in the learning process. Moreover we do see Researches from (Mansoor Ahmed Channa, 2015) enlightened with the efficacy of how to improve reading comprehension, use a pre-teaching vocabulary pre-questioning method and showed us that to support students in their academics we need to support students with effective reading strategies during comprehension activities, pupils who were not given any pre-reading strategy outscored those who were.

The characteristics of reading (Renandya, 2002) explain different ways that teachers themselves can write materials of ER suited for helping students with different backgrounds.

Read aloud; this option has been the game changer for English language learners as stated in the book. (Wawryk-Epp, 2004). Articulate words clearly, this cannot be emphasized more. The articulation and instruction given by the teacher needs to be clear and crisp, the teacher has to be a model in order to make sure students read and pronounce words clearly and efficiently.

In the same guide we see that it stated how teachers should provide books on tape, CD, or computer. The use of multimedia has always helped and gathered student's attention and understanding on learning of better comprehension.

Use of Dictionaries also has decreased and so when students don't bother looking into dictionaries the best and easy way to acquire strategies for students are included in read aloud applications. The applications help in learning new words and making students understand important and easy words through minimal to no effort. The best part of these dictionaries are they are easily accessible and students can gauge in a number of ways. Producing speech can be advanced; computers can speak, through computer generated speech synthesized or digitized. The synthesized speech is built up via an additive method that combines discrete phonemes into sound units that listeners would interpret as words. Nothing is prerecorded; the computer creates "speech" according to its program and if we look into the preservation and recall of prerecorded human speech is referred to as digitized speech.

The learning of a student is always enhanced if the environment is supporting their ideas and expressions, just like this when a student is facing difficulty in learning or understanding English, the student should be introduced to a better environment. So, if mobile applications are helping students in learning, it is not only because of excellent

graphics, vivid descriptions and illustrations but they change the outlook, they cancel the effect of the environment around them and continue the process of learning.

There was a reason for taking a biography; it was to learn from what the person goes through. Real life examples always create a better understanding, they make students seek the opportunities, challenges and risks one faces and more overcomes.

The Role of the "Get Epic" Platform in Digital Pedagogy

The "Get Epic" platform is a sophisticated Instructional System Program, providing educators with high-quality, curated content that bridges the gap between traditional literacy and digital engagement. Unlike static PDF readers, Get Epic offers a multi-platform interface (desktop and mobile) that aligns with the principles of Digital Ecology by centralizing resources and reducing the need for physical materials.

A critical factor in the successful implementation of MALL is the degree to which learners can navigate the software independently. Get Epic features a highly intuitive, user-friendly interface that requires minimal orientation from the instructor. This fosters learner agency, allowing students to engage with the material with little to no external assistance a major requirement for effective virtual and distance learning. The platform allows for significant teacher intervention and content curation. Instructors can:

- **Modify Assessments:** Teachers can edit quizzes and customize activity content to align with specific lesson objectives.
- **Differentiated Content:** The system enables teachers to select age-appropriate levels and specific content formats (fiction, biographies, instructional, or pleasure reading) assigned to each individual learner's needs.

- On-Screen Assistance: Real-time instructions are provided within the interface, offering scaffolded support for students as they navigate complex texts.

To prevent "digital fatigue" or progress loss, the platform includes robust technical safeguards. The instant saving and bookmarking features allow for a seamless learning experience; students can resume their work exactly where they left off without jeopardizing completed activities. The interface supports non-linear navigation, allowing learners to reread prior screens or adjust audio playback without restarting the module. One of the most significant highlights of Get Epic is its capacity for data-driven monitoring. The system generates individual student profiles that record:

- Progress Tracking: Detailed logs showing the number of books read and the time spent on each task.
- Assessment Scores: Teachers can access scores from customized quizzes, providing immediate feedback on student performance.
- Reading Logs: The software stores retrievable data on reading habits, which is essential for longitudinal assessment and institutional reporting.

Get Epic facilitates both individual and group-based virtual activities. By eliminating the need to "load and reload" materials, it ensures high engagement levels. More importantly, this transition to a digital reading log represents a sustainable pedagogical shift, replacing paper tracking with a permanent, electronically archived record of student achievement.

Teachers have historically maintained a complex relationship with technology. Some fear that the rapid advancement of mobile applications and Artificial Intelligence (AI) may

eventually marginalize the educator's role. However, this argument can be addressed by viewing technology not as a replacement, but as a catalyst for professional growth. If an educator resists technological integration, their pedagogical reach remains limited; conversely, by adopting these tools, teachers can work more efficiently, fostering independent and resilient learners.

Within a Digital Ecology, the teacher's role shifts from a traditional knowledge provider to a vital facilitator of a paperless learning environment. While mobile programs provide unique instructional opportunities such as "read-along" features and fluency support—they cannot replace the teacher's ability to pose perspective-driven questions and forge interconnections with real-life experiences.

Furthermore, the teacher is the essential architect of Educational Sustainability. By moving away from physical textbooks toward a digital-first strategy, educators lead the transition toward a more resource-efficient and ecologically responsible classroom. In this new era of blended learning, the application provides the data and accessibility, but the teacher provides the human insight and critical thinking that no software can replicate.

Chapter 3: Research Methodology

3.1 Type of the Research:

Mixed Method Research (Both Qualitative and Quantitative)

3.2 Population of the Study:

A population of research paper is a mixture of collection of data and information for different resources , A sample is refer to a certain portion of the population of interest as a whole , In this research paper the population of this study were the fifth grade students studying in Beacon house IB Campus , there are 72 branches of Beacon house all over the world .The main purpose objective of Beacon house is to seek the Light , the same way this metaphor used for knowledge helps in making new researches in the field of Education , where English language learning holds its own value.

3.3 Sampling Technique and Sample Size:

Probability sampling. This type of sampling is about a larger number of participants that were the whole 5th graders from which the Simple Random Sampling technique will be used to see all students of the 5th grade studying in the school beacon house 29 students being male and 21 female subjects.

3.4 Research Design:

Research design: this research utilizes a mixed-method research design which is specifically called a quasi-experimental approach. This research helps to evaluate the impact of mobile language learning on literacy.

The intervention begins with participants engaging with the "Get Epic" mobile application as a primary reading tool for a set. Following the interventions, the quantitative phase starts, where students complete a structured reading comprehension assessment designed to measure specific language outcomes, including vocabulary

acquisition and inferential listening. Now, how do we capture the learner's voice and evaluate the digital ecology of the tool, a Likert-scale questionnaire was administered in this phase. The aim was on qualitative and to understand the students' perception of accessibility and the effectiveness of the digital interface compared to the original materials

3.5 Research Instrument:

Digital Pedagogical Tool: The "Get Epic" mobile application was used as the primary instructional platform, providing a library of diverse, high-quality digital texts (e.g., *The Diary of Anne Frank*).

Attitudinal Questionnaire (Google Forms): A structured survey designed to gather quantitative data on student motivation, ease of use, and the perceived benefits of moving toward a paperless learning environment.

3.6 Reliability and Validity

For keeping the academic integrity of this study, several measures were taken to maintain high levels of reliability and validity: The research instruments (questionnaires and assessments) were designed like the "science of reading" principles as outlined by Duke and Pearson (2021). This made sure that the study accurately measures reading comprehension and vocabulary learning rather than peripheral digital skills. "Get Epic" application provided access to authentic, high-quality literary content, such as *The Diary of Anne Frank*. This aligned with international literary standards making sure that the data reflects real-world linguistic challenges faced by EFL (English as a Foreign Language) learners. By combining quantitative data from Google Forms with qualitative

insights from student feedback, the study obtains "data triangulation." This method reduces any bias and promises that the findings are consistent without change across different measurement tools. The findings are highly applicable to the current global educational borders. As said by Blau and Shamir-Inbal (2017) and UNESCO (2016), the shift to digital ecologies is a universal trend. This research is a valid framework for educators, English instructors, and software developers seeking to implement sustainable, mobile-first pedagogical strategies.

3.7 Significance of the Study

This study depicts a substantial value to the field of Applied Linguistics and Educational Technology. In the world of rapid digital transformation, this study can provide a practical roadmap for instructors/educators to transition from print-heavy methods to a sustainable digital ecology.

The study's ability to:

1. Empower Educators: Providing teachers with a clear methodology for selecting and inculcating authentic digital channels/websites for reading.
2. Motivate Learners: Showing how MALL can increase learners' engagement and "learner agency" in a virtual environment.
3. Support Sustainability: It also highlights how mobile applications serve as a paperless alternative, aligning EFL with global environmental goals.

Chapter 4: Data Analysis and Results

4.1 Overview of the Study

This chapter presents and analyzes the data collected regarding the impact of Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL) on 5th-grade students. The study focuses on the transition from book reading to the interactive mobile application "Get Epic" to assess improvements and attention in reading comprehension and developing student engagement.

4.2 Participant Profile (Demographics)

The study was conducted with a cohort of students from the primary section of a private school. The participants consisted of both male and female students, aged 11 to 12 years. Prior to the study, all participants were enrolled in a standard school reading program where they utilized basic PDF readers. This familiarity with digital helped in creating a baseline for observing the advanced features of the MALL intervention.

4.3 The Research Tool: "Get Epic"

Get Epic, is an industry-leading digital reading platform founded by Suren Markosian. Recognized in 2016 as a premier application for literacy development, the platform serves over 200 million subscribers globally. For the purpose of this research, the application was selected for its age-appropriate content (up to age 12) and its dual "Text Reading" and "Read Aloud" functionalities.

These features are critical for:

1. Eliminating the "fear of language" by giving scaffolded audio support.
2. Enhancing pronunciation and accent learning and listening through authentic audio models.
3. Providing both free and subscription-based plans to support inclusivity.

4.4 Data Collection Procedure

To make sure a well-structured digital ecology, teachers kept school-authorized email accounts for each participant. This allowed for seamless access to the application and enabled the teacher to track individual progress and records accurately. The experimental sessions were conducted during 50-minute class periods. A key observation given during this phase was the application's ability to support differentiated learning:

Standard Learners: They finished the assigned readings within the class period.

Differentiated Support: Slow learners were given extra time to complete the readings, highlighting the flexibility of mobile applications in giving diverse cognitive speeds and learning difficulties.

4.5 Assessment and Instrumentation

Following the reading of "The Diary of Anne Frank," students were administered a 13-item digital questionnaire. The questions tested the cognitive capacity of the 11-12 age group, focusing on:

Textual Comprehension: Monitoring understanding of the specific narrative.

App Evaluation: Gathering qualitative feedback on the "Get Epic" user experience.

Data was collected via Google Forms, allowing for real-time response tracking and quantitative analysis. The following sections detail the results derived from these responses.

Figure 1

The population was taken from Fifth graders studying in the private school system (Beacon house). All students were a part of a reading program that started in April. This reading group contains all the students who were made part of the reading club to help them with their reading and speaking skills. It has been observed that forceful reading cannot be done. Reading groups can only be successful if all the individuals are interested in it or are given a good and welcoming environment. It comes from inside. Corona virus outbreak and lockdown also contributed to the fact that schools around all the world. Students were confined to their homes as all classes were conducted online. This helps in their understanding of online apps which makes it easier and compulsory for students to be introducers to such apps. The next world is going to be all digital. Most of the libraries stopped working during lockdown. Readers mostly relied on the online readings on Google books and other websites. So the students who were really interested and wanted

to read more while staying at home during quarantine took part and further on helped in completing the reason effectively.

Figure 2

Question	Correct responses
Select the right choices. after publishing in 1947, Annes Diary ...	22 / 50

The question on selecting the right choices, Select the right choices. After publishing in 1947, Anne's Diary ... options were also given to the subjects so they can choose right or answer of their own choice.

Figure 3

13) Select the right choices.after publishing in 1947, Anne's Diary ... *

- Sold millions of copies
- Inspired a play
- Inspired a movie
- A museum was built on the building where she hid.
- She got flowers
- She was very happy and gave a big speech to show her happiness

was the frequently missed one,one aspect to be about it was it had checked boxes so students could have a possibility of missing out on the options, some students must have came up with a comprehensive understanding of the reading but then as seen in the frequently missed questions shows that some students followed the story more than the number of achievements Anne Frank had. The understanding of this also showed that students' learning was diversified when it came to details of any achievement. These answers show both aspects, one the student's perspective towards achievements was highlighted. The other thing is that the particular passage belongs to the last part of the text. It has been observed that most readers at this age lose their interest towards the end.

The book given to the learners was an autobiography; a glimpse of history in the time of Hitler. The autobiography is always difficult and tedious. Autobiographical works can really create a sense of realism and make it more relatable for the readers. The history of Anne Frank proves to be a strong relationship; it makes the learners connect their life

with her history. It shows the struggle of a woman in difficult circumstances especially in a historical context.

Figure 4

1) Which group of people took over the country of Germany in 1930s to 1940s.

48 / 50 correct responses

This question is to test the retention and knowledge understanding of the learners. The idea of retention is dependent on eliminating distraction and seen clearly by the results we see how subjects were able to distinguish between them, the options given were to improve the idea and facts of learning. Also the options were defined with the main groups in the book so they were interconnected with each other. The student's ratio of 96% shows students' interest in history.

Figure 5

2) Anne Franks was a
49 / 50 correct responses

The question presented above was given to assess the knowledge of the subjects and to be mentioned is the fact that never in the book. There was no specific title given to the main author of the story, the students through their understanding came up with a title and this concluded that students came up with a better conclusion. 98% students showed their understanding of information presented in and out of text.

Figure 6

3) Rearrange this paragraph to make sense of the story.
39 / 50 correct responses

This question was how to gist and rearrange the major events, majority of the 78% learners opted for the right gist of events, this highlights two important points, point one that majority of the learners were able to grasp the timeline of the history and sync the events properly.

The second point of interest was that the readers easily learnt major history events without any inhibition, no stops and no agitation was seen. The historical events were easily read even by the understanding of text and read aloud application helped in bridging the gap of any other inhibition. More skilled readers, on the other hand, may shift their focus to more abstract, conceptual concepts and make greater use of previous knowledge, relying on only as much textual information as is necessary for verifying and anticipating the information in the text. The descriptions of events and sequences nested within the reading comprehension within the causes and effects of the event it was easily underlined with the

Using the structure of the events it was seen that the organization to make meanings from the events was easily completed.

Figure 7

4) Fill in the right pronoun: "Later, Anne and Margot were sent together without ____ mother to the Bergen-Belsen."

44 / 50 correct responses

The reading comprehension understanding highlights one very major point that is local cohesion more easily explained, it tells us about how well sentence structure is formed in the mind of the reader. Following part or question is to check the grammar and language skills of students. It was to see how reading can help in understanding of language and grammar. As a result of these challenges, low-proficiency readers read at a slower rate than higher-proficiency readers. L2 readers employ semantic processing in addition to word and discourse level processing including lexical and contextual data.

The readers were able to distinguish the use of pronouns. Pronouns helped us in making more. The pronouns not only show their understanding but their correlations of

how they make the context clearer. The clarity is shown and not to forget very few experienced readers further on the other hand may shift their attention to more abstract, conceptual notions and make more use of prior knowledge, depending on only as much textual information as is essential for validating and predicting the information in the text. We here can conclude that learners do have a better and clear understanding of pronouns.

Figure 8

The word recognition and vocabulary is an essential part in reading and once we see the reading of the readers, we observe how well they can distinguish words and put up their understanding in the reading. The importance of vocabulary in reading comprehension is fascinating and complicated. To be able to form a mental picture of text, that is; to comprehend its meaning, one must be able to decode the written information. Slower and inefficient lexical access and semantic processing are frequently blamed for the gap between competent and less proficient readers. Findings on reading

processes and vocabulary threshold have continuously indicated the important impact and relevance of vocabulary knowledge in reading comprehension performance in the context of second language reading research. The same way we see this performance of words and vocabulary on reading being the most efficient tool that help readers in their understanding, this graph above shows how 92% of the majority learners were able to understand the new vocabulary word and they were able to understand it without any problem, so conclusion can be that words are easily learnt by the majority learners through online applications.

Figure 9

Question no 6 states that What did Anne Frank's Life made you realize?, This question was particularly asked to imply on the idea that how the author's life effects the main point of the work , when readers are able to make the connections they were able to see the picture in front of them, the story is about real life accounts of Anne frank which creates a realist point of view of the story , the subjects could correlate with the main

idea of the work, This is the main difference between fictional and auto biographical work, fictional work mostly creates an illusion because they are about some imaginary scenarios whereas the autobiographical accounts are almost true stories related to the author's life so they underline the major challenges a human face. The understanding of what is being read and how it is read is clearly seen, the conclusion made by the reader and how they understood major points of the reading can be summarized as some stated as Ancestry relating it to the history and future understanding readers being fifth graders were able to realize the major. Another subtopic we can see is she was seen as fighter to the subjects was 25% understanding they could see the challenges she faced made them put forward their understanding and learning. The other topic we see some students were pointing out the oppressing group of Nazi's that were relating to the main topic in which in the autobiography we see how the under related work is getting highlighted. Another topic was her being a good writer. It also implies the idea of the thinking pattern of a particular age group. They were not able to get the deep underlying theme but they got the idea according to their age group.

Figure 10

In reading literature, we have 7 to 9 Genres in fiction, this reading was mainly over Nonfiction in nonfiction we see the stories like

- Autobiography/Biography A genuine storey of a real person, told as a narrative of a person's life.
- Thesis: A brief literary writing that expresses the author's viewpoint or point of view.
- Storytelling: Nonfiction is a type of writing that is not Factual facts presented in a story-telling fashion. Nonfiction Informational text on a real-life topic.
- Speech: The term "speech" refers to a public address or a debate.

While reading the different genres came the understanding of them so this question no 7) The book you read on get epic about "Anne Frank" what type of genre was it? 43 / 46 correct responses, in the book it was not mentioned specifically that it was an autobiography here the subjects through their prior learning of knowledge and connecting inferences were able to relate and correlate between what account was the reading made on, the reading also showed how much objective clearance was in the readerts, the subjects could connect their cognizance to the reading comprehension.

Figure 11

8) What was Auschwitz-Birkenau?

45 / 50 correct responses

The question number 8 stated on What was Auschwitz-Birkenau?

The comprehension of this term was only possible if the readers, read important features and this understanding was shown on the idea of how the main clues could identify text structures, features and the language used, the same way when this question was asked the subjects could easily make connections with new language introduced also showed that the content was relevant and subjects could comprehend it according to their learning needs. The option also had answer options of a fireplace and a place in England. This was given to juggle the minds of the subjects as both were closely knitted together but majority of the readers were successful to comprehend the main crux of the idea.

Figure 12

9) What caused Anne's Franks Family to go into hiding?

44 / 50 correct responses

The question number 9) What caused Anne's Frank's Family to go into hiding? Underlined a very important aspect that was on cause and effect that shows a very crisp understanding of how well the reader can make connections and juggle with the main idea, the cause and effect also distinguish whether or not reader was interested in the reading , they were able to quantify major components and understand them . This question had options that could have been a very easy gateway for confusion but the subjects easily pointed out the hiding aspect. The call up notice was a very strong topic as it led to further deaths in the reading so it was easy for you to show the main highlights.

Figure 13

Some subjects presented the idea that “war” can be a theme. The violence presented in the story can be the reason for presenting war as a theme.

Some stated Independence as the main theme. This shows the subject’s deeper understanding of the text. The idea that people living in captivity yearn for freedom or independence.

Some stated slavery as an underlying main theme. This notion comes from the treatment of people as they were kept captive just like slaves. They were not allowed to act or say according to their own wishes.

Some stated captivity as the main theme as people were kept captive in confined places. They were seen as slaves. This is one of the most prominent themes of the text.

Some defined Adolf Hitler as a main theme. This is again related to the people who kept Nazi as the main theme. This shows their impact in the mind of a subject of a certain age.

This shows their understanding of ideas like freedom, captivity and hope. The reader showed empathy towards the author and their resentment towards the tyranny. It also gives an idea of how subjects were able to construct ideas like hope according to the

play. Subjects' understanding of abstract concepts such as happiness and kindness shows their ability to comprehend deeper ideas.

Figure 14

This question was given to subjects to see how much the subject can recall the main events.

The ability to decipher the text, understand it properly, and retain the information is referred to as recall. Only when the learner has sufficient previous knowledge and the material is near to their or her instructional reading level can this happen. Following question is taken from the text and 78% subjects were able to retain the information and were able to give the correct answer.

Figure 15

13) The word "concentration camps" synonym can be

44 / 48 correct responses

The synonym of the word “concentration camp” shows how much subjects have understood the text. This question was given to check the impact of reading and its understanding of students. With reading students were able to understand difficult words. By giving synonyms subjects have learned different meanings of the word. So reading not only helps in learning of new ideas but the word bank as well.

Figure 16

13) Select the right choices.after publishing in 1947, Annes Diary ...

22 / 50 correct responses

The right choices of the writing and after the publishing in 1947,

- Anne's Diary had a set of achievements:
- Sold millions of copies
- Inspired a play
- Inspired a movie
- A museum was built on the building where she hid.
- She got flowers
- She was very happy and gave a big speech to show her happiness

All the above 4 options were required, the answers showed that majority were able to comprehend what happened to her and how she ended up, the last two were tricky and given on purpose to see where through different use of pronouns and present tense would the subjects get confused, Only 6% ticked on the option “She got flowers” and 4% ticked upon A museum built on the building where she hid. This question shows that most of the students were able to retain the given information and comprehend new notions from it.

Furthermore adding, In reading comprehension we see that following aspects are noted:

1. Comparison: In this questionnaire we see a comparison of the research implemented on 6) What did Anne Frank's Life make you realize?

2. Cause and effect in this questionnaire we can lignite the effects in the question 9) what caused Anne's Frank's Family to go into hiding?

3. Problem and solution: The problem and sequence of events is always seen as a very important part of study on Language Learning as if a subject is able to decipher the problems of the text they try in comprehending solutions too. The question number 6) what did Anne Frank's Life make you realize? showed a problem \situation presented to subjects that they further on showed their solutions on

4. Sequence: The sequence of the reading comprehension should also be a very keen pointer it note as it helps learners in stating things or events accordingly without any gap of information , the basics of language learning implements such action words , or time sequence vocabulary that develops a more clear understanding of here and after events, Question 4) that stated to arrange the events, which helped in understanding whether the students have been able to sequence the events from History or not .

Reflection of the study

After finding how well the reading comprehension was supported from the online mobile application “Getepic “, understanding of the text has been recorded. After these students are instructed to press next and now the questionnaire evaluated the effects of mobile applications and subjects’ inhibitions, and acceptance towards them.

The first question asked was about do you like reading on the application “getepic”

Figure 17

Do you like reading on the application "getepic"
50 responses

The answer to this survey showed that 90% of the young learners were in favor of the application. This answer showed how much they appreciated the findings of literature review and it does support it. Once learners like a stimulus it becomes very easy for them to share their understanding and learn in a better way. Over the years teachers and instructors have observed the effects of the learning resources over the learners and this is

one of them. The uses off mobile applications help them in adapting and their learning process.

Figure 18

One challenge you faced while using "Getepic"

50 responses

The question asked by the survey was to analyze one challenge faced by the subjects. Question asked where to apprehend, what problems were to keep in mind when learners are using mobile applications.

Through the bar chart above you can distinguish how the Internet could be seen as a big obstacle in the lives of the learners. The subjects showed a little reservation due to

internet 28% subjects did show some issue now to keep in mind the demographic issues of Pakistan should be highlighted where the learners were accessing the mobile application , Pakistan being an underdeveloped country shows most of the people don't have access to proper internet access. The bandwidth of the Internet is also distributed very unequally. Looking at Karachi, observations show that Internet connectivity is still an issue , due to this the 28% Internet problem by the subjects can be seen as a very important aspect to be noted in the further future studies.

The second option that had a very important and pertinent role in the survey was off the technical support inbuilt in the mobile system that helps in supporting mobile applications, the basic requirement to support any mobile application for education purpose is the mobile should at least have an updated software being of apple or android, being in the latest update.

The mobile to at least have 2gb of mobile storage and support. Some pointers like this help in making facilitators feel ease while implementing.

Figure 19

This feature of getepic that attracted the learners helps in making evaluation to put forward more applications similar in view. The reasons why getepic can help is that 1) It has the read aloud feature for almost every word. 2) The meanings of words, even prepositions are clearly shown to be getepic. 3) The pictures and text that are merged so well together also show a very elaborated and easy learning, as visuals always provide a source of better learning. 4) The easy access to reading pointers also shows a very valuable insight that availability of material can make learning language easier. This graph also concludes that the learners of these unprecedented times can eliminate the gap of language learning if given right resources and tools

Research Methodology: Mixed-Methods Approach

This study has Mixed-Methods Research Design, integrating both Quantitative and Qualitative data collection techniques. This approach helps and tracks a comprehensive analysis of the impact of MALL on 5th-grade learners, providing solid statistical evidence and behavioral insights.

Quantitative Method (Objective Data)

The Quantitative phase focused on measurable outcomes and statistical trends. It uses the objective, closed-ended questions within the Google Form assessment, the study gathered data on the percentages of correct responses regarding the text (*The Diary of Anne Frank*), statistical evidence of vocabulary acquisition and prior knowledge retrieval and measurable data regarding the time spent on the "Get Epic" application and frequency of tool utilization.

Qualitative Method (Subjective Data)

The Qualitative phase sought to understand the "learner experience" through subjective, open-ended questions. This method allowed participants to express their perspectives in their own words, focusing on detailed feedback on the "Get Epic" user experience and ease of navigation. Insights into how the transition from physical books to a digital ecology affected the students' enthusiasm for reading and analyzing subjective responses to understand how students formed connections between the digital narrative and real-world contexts.

Data Triangulation and Sustainability

By merging these two methods, the research achieves Data Triangulation. The quantitative results provide the "what" (improved scores), while the qualitative results provide the "why" (increased engagement via the mobile interface). This holistic view is essential for documenting the transition toward sustainable, paperless pedagogies, as it proves that digital tools are not only more environmentally friendly but also psychologically and academically superior for the modern learner.

Chapter 5: Summary and Discussion

5.1 Summary of the Study

This research studies and explores the efficacy of Mobile-Assisted Language Learning (MALL) in enhancing reading comprehension among fifth-grade learners and showing sustainable ways of resource preservation. By utilizing the mobile application "Get Epic," fifty participants (aged 11-12) were engaged with a digital version of *The Diary of Anne*

Frank. A mixed-methods approach was taken in the study to evaluate both the cognitive results (quantitative) and the learners experience (qualitative).

5.2 Discussion of Quantitative Findings: Cognitive Literacy

The quantitative data was driven from the assessment showed a high level of textual comprehension and vocabulary retention. Participants successfully were able to identify the key historical facts regarding the German occupation and the life of Anne Frank. The assessment of pronouns and synonyms (e.g., "segregate," "concentration camps") revealed that the interactive nature of the MALL interface facilitated better vocabulary retention than traditional PDF readers. Students' ability to successfully rearrange narrative paragraphs shows that digital reading supports the development of "Global Comprehension" which is the ability to see the "big picture" of a reading.

5.3 Discussion of Qualitative Findings: The Digital Ecology

The qualitative reflections from the students indicates a significant change in learners attitude. Students also reported a "barely minimum difficulty" in navigation, and a glaring omission of "fear" or anxiety. This suggests that the MALL interface lowers the anxiety and affective filter which allows for a more resilient learning process. This high welcoming response to the application confirms that learners view smartphones as more than social devices and they are perceived as powerful, easy, accessible tools for academic growth.

5.4 Synthesis: MALL as a Tool for Sustainable Education

The findings of this study go beyond classroom performance. As noted during the COVID-19 pandemic, the scarcity of physical resources necessitated an immediate transition to digital alternatives. This research proves that such a transition is not just a temporary fix but a strong Sustainable Pedagogical Solution.

By utilizing Get Epic, the school transitioned into a Digital Ecology which made access to over 200 million subscribers' worth of content without the environmental cost of printing. The digital reading logs and Google Form assessments created a permanent, hassle free and waste-free record of student progress. The competence of students to "read on the go" ensures that learning continues despite of physical infrastructure limitations.

Conclusion:

This study on mobile assisted language learning specifically through mobile reading applications serves as a strong transformative tool for modern pedogeological landscapes. Providing immediate and universal access to literally resources these applications effectively help in bridging the gap between learners and authentic content. Indus research we conclude that increasingly digitalized era of mobile reading platforms are now not merely a supplementary tool but are a big key component for the future of sustainable literacy. Covid-19 has acted as a critical catalyst for the shift as physical libraries have become inaccessible and traditional schooling was highly disrupted. Through this, mobile applications have emerged as an essential digital lifeline. The platforms ensure educational continuity with a mobile-first approach, which is more

resilient than traditional models. From a digital ecology perspective the transition to mobile reading highly aligns with global sustainability mandates which promote paperless classrooms and reduce the environmental impact of physical book production and distribution. By offering dematerialized libraries at the readers' fingertips, mobile-assisted language learning empowers both students and facilitators to engage and collaborate in a learning process which is ecologically responsible, educationally effective and socially and sustainably innovative. Frameworks should definitely prioritize integration of digital channels which Foster a more resilient and a highly sustainable educational system

Findings & Recommendations:

The empirical analysis of this study has confirmed that mobile-assisted language learning is an indispensable asset for a highly increasing digitalized global society.

The study also identifies the mobile platforms significantly streamline the acquisition of core linguistic competencies such as vocabulary retention, reading comprehension and, specifically, pronunciation, and through this, they provide a more efficient and effective delivery system than the usual traditional methods. Key findings have also suggested that the integration of mobile applications enhances a smarter pedagogical approach, meaning it shifts this classroom dynamic towards active learning. Transition not only enhances but also develops student engagement and fosters a digital ecology where resources can be managed properly and sustainably. The ability of high-quality education content on demand helps in reducing the reliance on physical infrastructure, making language learning easy, resilient and accessible.

Based on the results of the study, some recommendations are proposed for enhancing the future of education.

Professional development: Educators are strongly encouraged to undergo specialised professional development courses which help them in increasing their digital literacy. Beyond the basic usage, an educator should become comfortable in utilising advanced online tools to facilitate a seamless and sustainable hybrid learning environment.

Cross-platform accessibility:

To make sure educational equity and sustainability are there, developing institutions should prioritize applications which are compatible with the persuasive range of mobile devices, ensuring that the hardware limitation does not become a barrier for the learning of the individuals

Offline functionality:

To prevent hindrances to the progress of learning, the study also recommends the implementation of offline modes. Meaning the modes which provide access to materials without constant internet connection also helping and ensuring that the learning process remains uninterrupted regardless of the users Geographic or socioeconomic location.

Interactive and data-driven design:

Mobile applications used for language learning should priorities high levels of interactivity to maintain the learner's motivation. More of these platforms have to include robust assessment modules to provide educators with the clear, data-driven record of the student's progress which further helps in developing the right skills that need more attention.

Cultivating and developing the digital mindset:

This is great for both learners and educators the great to develop and adapt new technologies. A proactive attitude and a 'learning never ends' mindset are required, which are very important for navigating the ongoing technological and organizational changes which are required within the modern education territories.

Implications of the Study:

The implications of this research extend across multiple dimensions of modern pedagogy, which offer frameworks for students, educators, and distance learners alike.

By leveraging the pervasive nature of mobile technology, this study can provide a solution for diverse learner profiles, which include those who struggle with traditional classroom environments or those who exhibit introverted social tendencies. This meaning can impinge on educational inclusivity. Flexibility of MALL allows for a personalized, low-anxiety space which supports emotional and cognitive needs

Overcoming barriers for distance education and virtual schooling, this research shows that mobile tools are essential for maintaining educational continuity. It also demonstrates that learning can even occur outside of a fixed territory, allowing students in remote or underserved regions to access high-quality linguistic resources without geographical constraints.

From practitioners in English language and literature, this study can also suggest that shifting towards a blended learning mode can empower teachers to modernize their instructional design. Write a road map for climbing to higher levels of pedagogical efficiency through technology such as data integrated apps.

The research study also carries significant implications for digital ecology, meaning it proposes a transition towards a more sustainable, paperless educational infrastructure. Adopting these findings institutions can highly reduce their physical resource consumption while preparing students for the organizational changes and technological expertise for 21st century.

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